

EFFECT OF STRAIN RATE ON TENSILE FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF FIBRE REINFORCED POLYAMIDE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Tensile testing of four different woven fabric polyamide composites was performed at various loading rates ranging from 1×10^{-3} to 3m/s using a servohydraulic testing apparatus. Two kinds of reinforcements, carbon fibre (CF) and glass fibre (GF), and two kinds of matrices, polyamide-6 (PA6) and modified polyamide-6 (mPA6), were the components of the four composites. The results showed that both tensile strength and failure strain of these composites tend to increase with increase of strain rate except for GF/mPA6 whose tensile strength and failure strain were stabilized at high rates ($>1 \times 10^0$ 1/s). Fracture regions of the tested specimens were also observed to study micromechanisms of tensile failure using a polarized optical microscope. The results showed that in the composites with mPA6 matrix, extensive microcracking occurred in the matrix regions prior to the final failure. Rate effects on the tensile fracture behaviour of the polyamide composites are discussed on the basis of these experimental results.

KEYWORDS: polyamide composites, tensile behaviour, strain rate dependence, high speed testing

INTRODUCTION

Dynamic tensile testing of continuous fibre reinforced polymer composites has been performed to characterize the tensile mechanical behaviour of the composites [1-6]. Dynamic mechanical properties such as elastic modulus, tensile strength and failure strain were obtained in these studies by using specific high speed tensile testing systems such as a one bar method [1], split-Hopkinson pressure bar techniques [2-5] and a falling weight impact tester [6]. Dynamic testing results are sometimes compared with static data obtained by different tests to study rate effects on the mechanical properties. On the other hand, as one attempt to extend static test to a higher rate test, Béguelin and Kausch have developed a high speed testing system using a modified servohydraulic testing machine and an optical extensometer [7]. They have applied this system to study rate effects on the tensile mechanical behaviour of polymers in a wide range of loading rates.

In the above studies, most of the attention were paid to thermoset matrix composites. With increasing interests in thermoplastics as matrices for polymer composites, many works have been carried out to characterize the mechanical behaviour of thermoplastic matrix composites; however, few attempts have been made to study the dynamic tensile behaviour of the composites. In the present study, dynamic tensile testing of continuous fibre reinforced

polyamide composites was carried out by means of the high speed testing system developed by Béguelin and Kausch, and effects of strain rate on the tensile fracture properties were investigated. In this paper, the experimental results are presented, and the tensile failure mechanisms of this type of thermoplastic matrix composites are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material and Specimen

Four different polyamide composites were studied in this work. Plain woven fibre cloth made of carbon fibre (CF) or E-glass fibre (GF) was used as the reinforcement in these composites. The matrix was polyamide-6 (PA6) or modified polyamide-6 (mPA6). It is known that mPA6 has higher stiffness and strength than PA6. The four composites are denoted hereafter by CF/PA6, CF/mPA6, GF/PA6 and GF/mPA6. Thin laminates of 1mm thickness containing six plies of reinforcements were fabricated for each material. The fibre volume fractions were 56% for CF/PA6 and CF/mPA6, 51% for GF/PA6 and 54 % for GF/mPA6. Tensile specimens were cut from the laminates, and the direction of the warp threads corresponded with the tensile loading direction. Specimen geometry is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Tensile specimen geometry (the thickness of the specimen is 1mm).

Testing Apparatus

Tensile testing of the four composites was carried out in a range of loading rate from 1×10^{-3} to 3 m/s using a servohydraulic testing machine. This apparatus has been modified so as to reduce dynamic effects at high rates of loading by using a viscoelastic damper in the loading unit [8]. A piezoelectric load cell was used for the measurement of load in high sensitivity. Strain was measured by means of an optical extensometer that was designed for the purpose of dynamic testing [8]. Two optical fibres were placed on specimen surface at an interval of 35 mm as shown in Fig.1, and the tensile deformation of the specimen was evaluated from the positions of two light points emitted through the optical fibres.

Microscopic Observation

Polarized optical microscopy (POM) was carried out to investigate fracture micromechanisms of the composites. Longitudinal cross sectional area near failure region was examined by

POM. For each of the four composites, a thin sample (about 100 μm thickness) was prepared from the failure region of a tested specimen by using cutting and polishing technique. The prepared samples were observed on a polarized optical microscope under transmitted and/or reflected light.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Testing

Stress-strain relations of four different polyamide composites obtained at the lowest loading rate (1×10^{-3} m/s) are shown in Fig.2. A knee phenomenon was observed for all four composites. It has been postulated that the nonlinearity in woven fabric composites is caused by micromechanical deformations such as shear deformation of the longitudinal threads, extensional deformation of the matrix regions and transverse cracking of the transverse threads [9,10]. It is clearly seen from Fig.2 that the nonlinear stress-strain behaviour after the knee

Fig.2: Stress-strain relations of four polyamide composites: (a) CF/PA6, (b) CF/mPA6, (c) GF/PA6 and (d) GF/mPA6.

Fig.2 (continued)

point was much larger in the glass fibre composites than that in the carbon fibre composites. Dependence of the initial tensile modulus on strain rate is shown in Fig.3. The tensile moduli of CF/PA6, CF/mPA6 and GF/PA6 tended to slightly increase as strain rate increased, while the modulus of GF/mPA6 appeared to be insensitive to strain rate.

Dependence of the tensile strength on strain rate is shown in Fig.4. The tensile strength of the carbon fibre composites increased with increase of strain rate. CF/mPA6 exhibited the highest tensile strength of all four composites at all strain rates as a result of the combination of high strength carbon fibre and mPA6 matrix. Thus, the better tensile properties of mPA6 than PA6 was well transferred to this type of composite system. The tensile strength of GF/PA6 also increased with increase of strain rate. The increase was 54% at the highest rate (4×10^1 1/s), while that of CF/PA6 was 28%. It should be noted that the tensile strength of GF/PA6 at the highest rate was almost equivalent to that of CF/mPA6, which possessed the highest strength at all rates. On the other hand, the tensile strength of GF/mPA6 increased as strain rate increased up to 1×10^0 1/s and then slightly decreased with increase of strain rate.

Fig.3: Dependence of the tensile modulus on strain rate for four polyamide composites.

Fig.4: Dependence of the tensile strength on strain rate for four polyamide composites.

Fig.5: Dependence of the failure strain on strain rate for four polyamide composites.

As a result, the strength of GF/mPA6 was equivalent to that of CF/PA6 and higher than that of GF/PA6 at the lowest rate (1×10^{-2} 1/s) but the least of all four composites at the highest rate (3×10^1 1/s).

Dependence of the failure strain on strain rate is shown in Fig.5. The failure strain of the glass fibre composites was larger than that of the carbon fibre composites as expected because glass fibre generally shows larger elongation than carbon fibre. The failure strain of the carbon fibre composites slightly increased with increase of strain rate. The failure strain of GF/PA6, on the other hand, increased as strain rate increased, whereas the failure strain of GF/mPA6 increased up to 1×10^0 1/s and then slightly decreased at higher rates. These strange odd rate dependencies on the tensile strength and the failure strain of GF/mPA6 appear to be related to the tensile failure mechanism of this composite discussed later.

Strain-rate dependence of the absorbed fracture energy is shown in Fig.6. The absorbed energy was directly estimated by numerical integration of the stress-strain curves. The absorbed energy for the glass fibre composites was higher than that of the carbon fibre composites at all strain rates tested, which is ascribed to the larger failure strain of the glass fibre composites as seen in Fig.5. Values of the absorbed energy for the carbon fibre composites and GF/PA6 tended to increase with increase of strain rate. However, the rate dependence for GF/mPA6 was very similar to those of the tensile strength (Fig.4) and the failure strain (Fig.5). Thus, it appears that the modified polyamide resin mPA6 fulfills its superior tensile performance as a matrix for carbon fibre composite at all strain rates tested. On the other hand, mPA6 loses its good function as a matrix for glass fibre composite under high strain rates ($>1 \times 10^0$ 1/s).

Fig.6: Dependence of the absorbed fracture energy on strain rate for four polyamide composites.

Fracture Mechanism

Failure regions of the carbon fibre composites at the highest loading rate (3 m/s) are shown in Fig. 7. For CF/PA6, a relatively straight fracture line perpendicular to the tensile direction was observed, whereas pull-outs of fibre bundles were significant in CF/mPA6. This tendency was seen at all the testing rates. Failure regions of the glass fibre composites at the highest loading rate (3 m/s) observed under transmitted light are shown in Fig.8. Dark regions in these photographs are thought to correspond to the damages such as matrix cracking, debonding, interfacial failure and delamination. More extensive damage zone was clearly observed in

Fig. 7: Failure regions of carbon fibre polyamide composites at a high loading rate (3 m/s):
(a) CF/PA6 and (b) CF/mPA6.

Fig. 8: Failure regions of glass fibre polyamide composites at a high loading rate (3 m/s):
(a) GF/PA6 and (b) GF/mPA6.

Fig.9: POM photographs of the failure regions for carbon fibre polyamide composites at a high loading rate (3 m/s): (a) CF/PA6 and (b) CF/mPA6.

Fig.10: POM photographs of the failure regions for glass fibre polyamide composites at a high loading rate (3 m/s): (a) GF/PA6 and (b) GF/mPA6.

GF/mPA6 than that in GF/PA6. The damage development prior to the final tensile failure of GF/mPA6 was larger than that of GF/PA6 at all testing rates.

POM photographs of the failure regions of the carbon fibre composites at the highest loading rate (3 m/s) are shown in Fig.9. For CF/mPA6, microcracks were formed perpendicular to the tensile direction and they were observed in the matrix regions and the transverse threads. It is also seen that these cracks propagated toward the interface between the longitudinal threads and the transverse threads. As a result, interfacial debonding must be generated. On the other hand, such kinds of failure modes were not observed in CF/PA6. POM photographs of the failure regions of the glass fibre composites generated at the highest loading rate (3 m/s) are shown in Fig.10. For GF/mPA6, extensive microcracks were observed in both the matrix regions and the transverse threads. Interfacial debonding and delamination were also seen in GF/mPA6. For GF/PA6, only a few cracks were initiated at the fracture point. At all the loading rates, microdamage formation was observed in both the carbon and the glass fibre composites with mPA6 matrix. Thus, the modified polyamide composites tended to generate microcracking in the matrix regions and also in the transverse threads under tensile loading condition. This may be related to the brittleness of mPA6. As seen in Figs.4, 5 and 6, the tensile failure properties of the carbon fibre composites could be improved by using mPA6 as a matrix at any testing rates. It is therefore considered that the microdamages observed in CF/mPA6 (Fig.9 (b)) did not affect the tensile fracture properties. On the other hand, in the case of GF/mPA6 (Fig.10 (b)), extensive microcracking occurred prior to the final failure and it prevented the increase of the tensile strength under high strain rates ($>1 \times 10^0$ 1/s), although GF/mPA6 showed better tensile performance at low loading rates ($<1 \times 10^0$ 1/s).

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile fracture properties of four different polyamide composites were studied at loading rates from 1×10^{-3} to 3 m/s using a high speed tensile testing apparatus. Carbon fibre composite with modified polyamide-6 matrix showed better tensile performance at all testing rates than carbon fibre composite with polyamide-6 matrix. Tensile mechanical properties such as tensile strength, failure strain and absorbed failure energy for both the carbon fibre composites tended to increase with increase of strain rate. Glass fibre composite with polyamide-6 matrix showed superior tensile performance especially at higher strain rates. The tensile mechanical properties of this composite dramatically increased as strain rate increased. On the other hand, the tensile mechanical properties of glass fibre composite with modified polyamide-6 matrix increased as strain rate increased up to 1×10^0 1/s and then slightly decreased at higher strain rates ($>1 \times 10^0$ 1/s). As a result, the mechanical properties of the modified composite were higher than those of the unmodified composite at low rates ($<1 \times 10^0$ 1/s). However, the relation was reversed at higher rates ($>1 \times 10^0$ 1/s). Extensive microdamage formation observed in the modified composite was related to this kind of rate dependence.

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